

The Influence of Green Product, Green Advertising, and Green Brand on Decision to Buy Through Consumers' Trust in Tupperware Products at SMPN Beureunerun

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ABSTRACT

The exiting threat on environment has caused many companies to apply new business concept on environment, called green marketing, a concept which includes all marketing activities to stimulate and to maintain consumers' environmentally friendly behavior. Some develop countries have applied regulation of green product, clean product in the process of production which domestically very significant so that they can compete with foreign products in which supplier, producers and consumers can understand this concept which has been applied by developed countries. Actually, this concept causes producers to spend more money, but it has bright future for them. The objective of the research was to find out and to analyze the influence of green product, green advertising, and green brand on decision to buy, either directly or through trust. Primary data were obtained from 75 respondents and analyzed by using path analysis with SPSS software program. The result of the research showed that partially, green product, green advertising, and green brand had positive and significant influence on decision to buy Tupperware product through consumers' trust at SMPN Beureuneun. Green product, green brand and trust had positive and significant influence on decision to buy Tupperware product through consumers' trust at SMPN Beureuneun. Green product, green advertising and green brand, and trust simultaneously had the influence on decision to buy product through consumers' trust at SMPN Beureuneun.

Keywords: Green Product, Green Advertising, Green Brand, Trust, Decision to Buy

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, various issues have emerged in the global community regarding environmental issues, such as environmental pollution, forest destruction, and global warming. Many factors are considered to be the cause of problems regarding the environment, including industrial and technological developments. In addition to providing a positive impact, the development of industry and technology also has a negative impact in the long run

that causes environmental damage and global warming (Pratama, 2014).

The causes of environmental damage in general can be categorized into two factors, namely due to natural and human-caused events. Volcanic eruptions, floods, abrasions, landslides, tornadoes, earthquakes and tsunamis are just a few examples of natural disasters. These disasters are the cause of environmental damage due to natural events. Even if it is examined further, disasters such as floods, abrasions, forest fires, and landslides can

occur because of human intervention. The second cause of environmental damage is due to human activity. Damage caused by humans is actually greater than the damage caused by natural disasters. This is because the damage done can occur continuously and tends to increase. This damage is generally caused by human activities that are not environmentally friendly such as forest destruction and forest conversion, mining, air, water and soil pollution and so forth. The following figure 1.1 shows the destructive actor / environmental polluter.

Source: Indonesian Forum for the Environment (2012)
Figure 1.1 Main Actors of destroyers / environmental polluters

The highest principal perpetrators of environmental destruction are companies. The damage contribution reaches 70 percent. Then followed by the government and the community, while the third largest environmental destroyer actors, namely companies and government, followed later is the combination.

The era of globalization has changed the traditional lifestyle towards modernization and technological sophistication. Various practical and instant ways are more people's choices in all aspects (Riska, 2010). One of the most talked about issues is global warming. Therefore, an environmental identification is needed to find out the biggest contributors to the environment and various efforts to protect the environment by applying the green concept. Green Consumerism, as a continuation of the global consumerism movement that starts from the awareness of

consumers of their rights to get a decent and safe product. This consumer awareness is formed because of patterns of behavior that are responsible for the environment and respect for the existence of other beings on this earth. Consumer awareness regarding the quality of the environment and the maintenance of natural resources in living conditions will ensure the balance and sustainability of nature and its environment. The business world in carrying out its business hopes that it will be able to generate decent profits for the company. However these benefits must be within reasonable limits and do not violate the rules of the game. Besides that the business activities must also be able to maintain environmental sustainability, not use excessive natural resources regardless of efficiency and not cause noise, water and air pollution, so ethics in business is needed.

The emergence of various threats to the environment, makes companies need to apply a new business concept by applying issues regarding the environment or called green marketing (Chen & Chang, 2013). Green marketing is a concept that encompasses all marketing activities developed to stimulate and maintain consumer behavior that is environmentally friendly.

There are five reasons for companies to develop green marketing: (1) according to environmental pressures, (2) obtaining competitive advantage, (3) increasing company image, (4) seeking new markets or opportunities, and (5) increasing product value (Chen, 2009).

At present there are not many companies that use the green marketing concept because of the various problems that will be faced. In the application of green marketing there are several problems that will be faced: (1) companies that use green marketing must be sure that their actions do not mislead consumers and industry, and do not violate regulations or laws that apply to marketing environment, (2) when modifying , their products are in accordance with consumer demand or perception, but it turns

out this product is also no better than the previous product because consumers have the wrong perception, and (3) government regulations designed to provide opportunities for consumers to make better, or motivating decisions they are more responsible for the environment.

In some developed countries it has applied environmental regulations about green products. Clean products in the production process have a very significant concept in the country so that local products can compete abroad where suppliers, producers, and consumers can understand this concept, because it has been a long time since producers - producers from developed countries have implemented it. The application of this will potentially have the effect of increasing budget costs for producers, but in the future it will also provide significant benefits as well.

Beureunuen District is one of the cities that is always active in promoting environmentally friendly activities. The application of the green living concept starts from the world of education from elementary school to high school. SMPN 1 Beureunuen, SMPN 2 Beureunuen and SMPN 3 Beureunuen are some of the schools included in the school that apply the green living concept in Beureunuen. The application of this environmentally friendly concept is carried out by all levels of teaching staff and students.

The ranks of staff and instructors at the SMPN in Beureunuen promoted the concept to students in the schools they taught starting with themselves. Their eco-friendly concept starts with a healthy and

clean lifestyle, in addition to the mandatory Local Government program that requires schools to have a green scope by planting trees in the school area. This awareness is offset by the obligation to dispose of garbage while classifying it according to the type of waste. While personally, their eco-friendly lifestyle is implemented by reducing plastic waste and other packaging waste. The concept of environmentally friendly living is also shown by the attitudes and habits of teachers and staff who use products that also apply environmentally friendly concepts such as Tupperware. Tupperware reflects its products into three fields, namely healthcare, lifestyle, and lighting. The fields developed by Tupperware are health and lifestyle. Tupperware creates health product innovations by making plastic products with safe materials and with a stylist model.

Tupperware applies the green marketing concept by making green products or environmentally friendly products, namely in the form of raw materials for products that are safe for health and environmentally friendly. Tupperware products are an innovation to enhance the company's competitive advantage. An innovation in the form of a green product has advantages over other products. Green products are usually durable, non-toxic, and made from recycled materials (Remedios, 2012). The advantage of Tupperware products is that they are environmentally friendly and last a long time. This has a positive impact on sales. The following is a data line of teachers and staff who use Tupperware products.

Table 1.1 Use of Pruduk Tupperware in the State Middle School Staff and Teachers in Beureunuen

No		SMP N 1	SMP N 2	SMP N 3
1	Permanent Teacher	38	31	35
2	Honor Teacher	27	22	25
3	Adminsitration Staff	6	7	5
Total		71	60	61
Total Staff & Teachers Overall		71	60	61

Based on table 1.1 above it is known that the number of staff and teachers using Tupperware products is very large. This is based on the interest of teachers and staff

for Tupperware products that offer an environmentally friendly concept. Tupperware has been successfully trusted by consumers in marketing their products

with environmentally friendly concepts by convincing consumers to recycle damaged Tupperware products by exchanging damaged products to the closest Tupperware distributor. Junaedi (2005) an important concept in implementing a green product is minimizing consumer disappointment so that consumers try and buy a green product, consumers usually feel that many attributes make a product good.

The application of the green marketing concept of Tupperware products in the business is considered to have a positive impact and is able to influence consumer purchasing decisions. Green marketing carried out by companies has a positive impact on the company, including: increased sales, improved feedback from customers, closer to customers, enhanced competitiveness, and improved corporate image. This is contrary to the statement of Mangonko (2011) which states that the

value of green marketing is not a measure of consumers or customers to buy a product.

In the world of production has a new policy in utilizing the resources around as much as possible and can dispose of minimal waste in the green product concept or also called ecolabeling. There are phenomena regarding some obstacles in the application of green products in Indonesia, such as the lack of awareness of producers, doubts about products labeled as green products and products labeled as green products are relatively more expensive. Likewise the case with the marketed Tupperware products has a higher price than other products that have almost the same function.

Several statements were submitted to teachers and staff at SMPN Beureunuen regarding the green product concept as follows.

Table 1.2 Results of Pre Survey of Green Product Variables

No	Statement	Agree		Disagree		Total
		Frek.	%	Frek.	%	
1	The price you pay is in line with the benefits of the Tupperware product	15	75	5	25	20
2	Tupperware products are proven to be a reliable environmentally friendly product	18	90	2	10	20
3	You are comfortable using Tupperware products	16	80	4	20	20
4	Tupperware products are safe for health and safety	20	100	0	0	20
5	Tupperware products are easy to buy	17	85	3	15	20

Based on table 1.2 above, it is known that the response of teachers and staff at SMPN Beureunuen understands the green product concept offered by Tupperware products both in terms of price compatibility with perceived benefits, product performance as evidenced by proving Tupperware products as environmentally friendly products, convenience of product use Tupperware, health and safety of the use of Tupperware products and ease in obtaining Tupperware products. From the statement submitted more than 75% of respondents answered agreeing with the statement submitted.

Research on green products has also been conducted by Pratama (2013), with the title "Effect of Green Product and Green Advertising on Purchasing Decisions of Superindo Consumer Supermarkets in Metro Branch Bandung". The results of

these studies indicate that green products partially have a significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions. The opposite study of green products has been carried out by Purnama and Nurhadi (2014). The results in his research state that, green products do not affect the decision to purchase bottled water (bottled water) products. Consumers who consume bottled water products prioritize the perception of product names, the quality of the mountain water and the water not mixed with harmful chemicals found on the packaging.

Tupperware products that are known for being environmentally friendly are marketed with the theme of environmentally friendly marketing. Tupperware makes an environmental-friendly advertisement called green advertising. The advertisement explains that consumers will feel a life free from worry by using Tupperware because it

has a long product life, materials made from materials are safe, and friendly to the environment. Advertising plays an important role in influencing consumers to buy a green product. There is a lot of attention to providing detailed information

and the actual benefits of green products in the green advertisements (Ankit and Mayur, 2013). Based on the pre-survey conducted the respondents' understanding of the green advertising of Tupperware products is explained as follows.

Table 1.3 Results of Pre Survey of Variable Green Advertising

No	Statement	Agree		Disagree		Total
		Frek.	%	Frek.	%	
1	Tupperware shows a concern for the environment	20	100	0	0	20
2	Tupperware promotes an eco-friendly lifestyle	20	100	0	0	20
3	Tupperware conveyed a message to always protect the environment	17	85	3	15	20

Table 1.3 above shows that the successful concept of green advertising was delivered to teachers and staff at SMPN Beureunuen. Almost all teachers and staff understand the message that Tupperware delivered through the advertisements it did.

Purnama and Nurhadi (2014) conducted a study of the effect of green products, green brand attributes, green advertising and premium price perceptions on purchasing decisions on bottled drinking water products. The study used 100 respondents. The results of the study stated that green advertising or environmental care ads affect the purchasing decisions of bottled water products.

In contrast, research conducted by Tias (2013) analyzed the effect of green advertising and green products on consumer involvement and its impact on customer purchasing decisions on Ades mineral water at the University of Indonesia Depok. The respondents used were as many as 100 people. In this study states that partially green advertising does not affect the purchasing decisions of consumers of Ades mineral water.

Consumers who are interested in caring for the environment generally think skeptically about green advertising or environmental care advertising. Green advertising needs to be done well and

precisely. A green advertising campaign must be related to clear, transparent and understandable environmental claims so that companies can attract consumers' attention (Ankit and Mayur, 2013). Green advertising on companies has an important role, namely as an image of the product in improving consumer perceptions. According to Rahim (2012), green advertising is an advertisement that aims to promote products or services, ideas or abilities companies in reducing environmental damage and pollution. Green advertising serves to provide special imaging for companies regarding green products that aim to care for the environment. Companies through green advertising introduce the image to the public about the marketed green product so that consumers can get to know the green product more deeply.

Green advertising or environmental care ads that are communicated appropriately will facilitate a green brand or a green brand embedded in the minds of consumers. This will change consumer perceptions, so that it will influence consumer purchasing decisions. Perception about green brand is one of the strategies carried out by the company that the brand simply does not see aspects of profit but also looks at environmental aspects (Praharjo, 2013).

Table 1.4 Results of Pre-Survey of Green Brand Variables

No	Statement	Agree		Disagree		Total
		Frek.	%	Frek.	%	
1	Tupperware has high credibility in maintaining a good commitment to the environment.	17	85	3	15	20
2	Tupperware has a good reputation for the environment.	18	90	2	10	20
3	You buy tupperware products because you believe Tupperware products can make environmental-friendly product expectations real	18	90	2	10	20
4	You are satisfied to buy Tupperware products and feel that the promised product is real	20	100	0	0	20
5	Tupperware is a product that is environmentally responsible	16	80	4	20	20

The pre survey results show that the green brand variable is indeed successful, making consumers understand the environmentally friendly concepts that are applied to Tupperware products. This is evidenced by the answer of the dominant respondent who agrees to the statement made.

Almaulidta (2015) in his research, explained the effect of green brands on purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction of Sony electronic products. The study used 116 respondents. The results of the study explained that there was a significant effect between the green brand and the purchasing decision of 37.5%.

This is contrary to previous research conducted by Braimah and Tweneboah-Koduah (2011), entitled "An Exploratory

Study of the Impact of Green Brand Awareness on Consumer Purchase Decisions in Ghana". The total number of respondents used in the study was 200 people. The results of the study indicate that the level of awareness of the green brand is relatively low in Ghana, and even the effect of awareness of the green brand on purchasing decisions is shown in lower numbers.

Trust will affect the purchase intention of prospective consumers / users, if the trust in a brand is good then the purchase intention will increase. The belief in the use of Tupperware products is no doubt this is evidenced by the results of the pre survey conducted. The pre survey results regarding the trust variables are as follows.

Table 1.5 Results of Pre Survey of Trust Variables

No	Statement	Agree		Disagree		Total
		Frek.	%	Frek.	%	
1	Tupperware is already known as an environmentally friendly product	15	75	5	25	20
2	Advertising delivered in accordance with available products	19	95	1	5	20
3	Tupperware products provide good after-sales service	16	80	4	20	20
4	The quality of Tupperware products throughout the world is undoubted	17	85	3	15	20

The pre-survey results showed that SMPN Beureunuen teachers and staff believed in Tupperware products. This can be seen from the answers of respondents who more than 75% agreed with the statement submitted. Based on the results of the pre-survey variations and several theoretical studies conducted on empirical studies conducted by several studies, the authors were interested in researching entitled "The Influence Of Green Product, Green Advertising, And Green Brand On Decision To Buy Through Consumers' Trust In Tupperware Products At SMPN Beureunerun".

Hypothesis

Based on the research background and the identification of the relationships between variables, the research hypothesis is as follows:

1. Green product has a positive and significant effect on consumer confidence in Tupperware products.
2. Green advertising has a positive and significant influence on consumer confidence in Tupperware products.
3. Green brands have a positive and significant influence on consumer confidence in Tupperware products.
4. Green product has a positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase Tupperware products.
5. Green advertising has a positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase Tupperware products.
6. Green brands have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions of Tupperware products.
7. Trust has a positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase Tupperware products.

8. Green product has a significant effect on purchasing decisions through consumer confidence in Tupperware Products.
9. Green advertising has a significant effect on purchasing decisions through consumer confidence in Tupperware Products.
10. Green brands have a significant effect on purchasing decisions through consumer confidence in Tupperware Products

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted to test the hypothesis proposed by using research methods that have been designed in accordance with the variables to be studied so that accurate results are obtained. This type of research is descriptive causal. According to Sinulingga (2014) that causal descriptive research is a study conducted to investigate causal relationships by observing the consequences that occur and the possible factors (causes) that cause these effects.

The nature of this research is research that explains the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing. This is in accordance with the purpose of the study, namely to explain the causal relationship that occurs between exogenous variables and endogenous variables by testing the hypothesis.

The population in this study were all teachers who were registered as teachers who had bought and used Tupperware products more than once, namely as many as 75 people. Sampling in the study used saturated sampling where the entire population was sampled as many as 75 teachers who were registered as instructors.

The data used in this study are Primary Data and Secondary Data. Primary data is data collected from original sources for specific purposes (Kuncoro, 2009). Secondary data is primary data that has been further processed (Umar, 2008). In this study, the secondary data used was obtained

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

The results of heteroscedasticity testing can be seen in Table 4.14 are as follows:

from official documents published through documentation studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Classical Assumptions Test for Substructure I

Normality Test Results

The results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov approach carried out are shown in Table 4.12

Table 4.12 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		75
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.07602114
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.065
	Positive	.065
	Negative	-.059
Test Statistic		.065
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

In Table 4.12 explains that the value of Significant Asym (2-tailed) is worth more than 0.05, meaning that data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test Results

Multicollinearity test is performed using SPSS 16 for Windows, can be seen in the following Table 4.13:

Table 4.13 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Green_Product	.396	2.524
	Green_Adv	.571	1.751
	Green_Brand	.346	2.890

Source: Research Results, 2018 (Data processed)

Based on Table 4.13 the results of data analysis in substructure 1 are known that the tolerance value of each variable is greater than 0.1 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) on each variable is smaller than 10. Then it can be concluded that further analysis can use the model multiple regression.

Table 4.14 Substructure Heteroscedasticity Test 1

			Green_Product	Green_Adv	Green_Brand	ABS_Kepercayaan
Spearman's rho	Green_Product	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.567	.750	-.068
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.561
		N	75	75	75	75
	Green_Adv	Correlation Coefficient	.567	1.000	.621	-.019
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.873
		N	75	75	75	75
	Green_Brand	Correlation Coefficient	.750	.621	1.000	-.311
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.067
		N	75	75	75	75
	ABS_Trust	Correlation Coefficient	-.068	-.019	-.131	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.561	.873	.067	.
		N	75	75	75	75

Source: Research Results, 2018 (data processed)

Based on Table 4.14 it is known that the heteroscedasticity test results show the value of the correlation significance of each variable more than 0.05. This means there is no homoscedasticity in this study.

Classical Substructure II Test Results Normality Test Results

The results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov approach carried out are shown in Table 4.15

Table 4.15 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		75
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.07602114
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.065
	Positive	.065
	Negative	-.059
Test Statistic		.065
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

In Table 4.15 explains that the value of Significant Asym (2-tailed) is worth more than 0.05, meaning that data is normally distributed

Multicollinearity Test Results

Multicollinearity tests are performed using SPSS 16 for Windows, can be seen in Table 4.16 below:

Table 4.16 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Green_Product	.347	2.881
	Green_Adv	.539	1.854
	Green_Brand	.275	3.640
	Trust	.279	3.583

Based on Table 4.16, the results of data analysis in substructure 1 show that the tolerance value of each variable is greater than 0.1 and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) in each variable is smaller than 10. Then it can be concluded that further analysis can use the model multiple regression.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

The results of heteroscedasticity testing can be seen in table 4.17. Based on Table 4.17, it is known that the results of heteroscedasticity test show the value of the correlation significance of each variable more than 0.05. This means that homoscedasticity did not occur in this study

Table 4.17 Substructure Heteroscedasticity Test 1

			Green_Product	Green_Adv	Green_Brand	Trust	ABS_Decision
Spearman's rho	Green_Product	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.567	.750	.754	-.103
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.379
		N	75	75	75	75	75
	Green_Adv	Correlation Coefficient	.567	1.000	.621	.645	-.113
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.335
		N	75	75	75	75	75
	Green_Brand	Correlation Coefficient	.750	.621	1.000	.780	-.229
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.059
		N	75	75	75	75	75
	Trust	Correlation Coefficient	.754	.645	.780	1.000	-.151
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.197
		N	75	75	75	75	75
	ABS_Decision	Correlation Coefficient	-.103	-.113	-.229	-.151	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.379	.335	.059	.197	.
		N	75	75	75	75	75

Source: Research Results, 2018 (data processed)

Hypothesis Test Results

Substructure Hypothesis I Test Results

Partial Test Results (t Test)

Based on Table 4.10 Substructure I can be explained as follows:

1. The value of the calculation of the green product is 3.168 and the significant value for the green product is 0.002 $\alpha 0.05$, so the green product variable has a positive and significant effect on trust, thus the hypothesis is accepted.
2. The value of the calculation of the green advertising variable is 2.041 and the significant value for green advertising is 0.045 $\alpha 0.05$, so the green advertising variable has a positive and significant effect on trust so the hypothesis is accepted.
3. The value of the calculation of the green brand is 4.290 and the significant value for the green brand is 0.000 $\alpha 0.05$, so the green brand variable has a positive and significant effect on trust, thus the hypothesis is accepted

Results of Substructure II Hypothesis

Partial Test Results (t Test)

Based on Table 4.11 Substructure 1 can be explained as follows:

1. The value of the calculation of the green product is 3.723 and the significant value for the green product is 0.000 $\alpha 0.05$, so the green product variable has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, thus the hypothesis is accepted.
2. The value of the calculation of the green advertising variable is 1.102 and the significant value for green advertising is 0.274 > - 3. The value of the calculation of the green brand is 3.465 and the significant value for the green brand is 0.001 $\alpha 0.05$, so the green brand variable has a positive and not significant effect on purchasing decisions, thus the hypothesis is accepted.
- 4. The t-count value of the trust variable is 4,559 and the significant value for the trust is 0,000 $\alpha 0,05$, so that the trust variable has a positive and significant effect on the purchasing decision thus the hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Table 4.18 Conclusion of Path Analysis Results

No	Variabel	Direct		Indirect	Conclusion
		Trust	Buying Decision		
1	Green product	0,316 (0,002)	0,280 (0,000)	0,120***	Intervening
2	Green advertising	0,170 (0,045)	0,066 (0,274)	0,064***	Intervening
3	Green brand	0,457 (0,000)	0,292 (0,001)	0,174***	Intervening
4	Trust		0,382 (0,000)		

Source: Research Results, 2018 (data processed)

The conclusion of the study shows that the trust variable functions as an intervening variable on the variables green product, green advertising and green brand. The discussion of the results of this study is further as follows:

Effect of Product Green on Trust

The results showed that directly that green products have a positive and significant effect on trust. This shows that every increase in green products will also

increase consumer confidence in Tupperware products. This has an increasingly good meaning for environmentally friendly Tupperware products, so consumers will increasingly trust the product.

The mean green product of 2.99 respondents' answers indicates that respondents disagree with Tupperware products having performance as environmentally friendly products. Tupperware is an environmentally friendly

product, this is confirmed by the company with Tupperware raw material that meets the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) standards of the USA and is environmentally friendly and safe for the health of its users. However, this does not make consumers believe in the safety of Tupperware products. This is because the Tupperware raw material made from plastic even though it has FDA standards does not make respondents answer by agreeing that the plastic is safe for the environment.

One of the green concepts of the Tupperware product that made consumers believe that Tupperware was an environmentally friendly product was that the Tupperware Company reprocessed the damaged waste of Tupperware products from consumers to be processed into new products. In addition, Tupperware is also made from raw materials that are environmentally friendly.

Kasali (2005) green product as an illustration of goods or products produced by producers that are related to security and do not have an impact on human health and do not have the potential to damage the environment. Green products are created to meet consumer needs for products that can guarantee safety and health. As is the case with Tupperware products that have been created as environmentally friendly concepts, which are increasingly safe for health and the environment, consumers will increasingly believe in the performance of Tupperware products as environmentally friendly and health-safe products.

This research is in line with the research conducted by Gil and Depar (2018) which proves that green products have a positive and significant effect on trust. Green product which is appointed about environmentally friendly product quality is trusted by consumers, especially by consumers who maintain health and care for the environment.

Effect of Green Advertising on Trust

The results showed that directly that green advertising had a positive and

significant effect on trust. This shows that every increase in green advertising will also increase consumer confidence in Tupperware products. This means that the easier consumers are to capture the eco-friendly messages conveyed, the more consumers will trust Tupperware products.

The average mean green advertising value of 3.25 respondents' answers shows that respondents disagree with the concept of environmentally friendly advertising delivered by Tupperware. The delivery of message advertisements on advertisements applied by Tupperware currently does not make consumers accept the message Tupperware delivered regarding the environmentally friendly concept.

Ankit and Mayur (2013) consumers who are interested in caring for the environment generally think skeptically about green advertising or green advertising. Green advertising needs to be done well and right. A green advertising campaign must be related to clear, transparent and understandable environmental claims so that companies can attract consumers' attention. Green advertising on companies has an important role, namely as an image of the product in improving consumer perceptions. According to Rahim (2012), green advertising is an advertisement that aims to promote products and services, ideas or the company's ability to reduce environmental damage and pollution.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by D'Souza (2005) which shows that there is a significant difference from the attitude of green advertising for consumers who are involved high and low. Based on cognitive evaluations from high-involvement consumers stated that green advertising is included in the believable and favorable category and based on affective evaluation, consumers consider that consumer advertising is in the good category. But, on cognitive evaluation, advertisements fall into the convincing category and on affective evaluations, advertisements fall into the pleasant category, the two groups

are rather neutral in their opinions about green advertisements being pleasant and their beliefs in green advertising convincing. While low-involved consumers generally disagree that green advertising is good, believable and favorable. Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that only groups that are slightly involved will be given a bad attitude toward green brand advertising. This can be interpreted in two ways. First, these consumers may not be interested in green advertising because they do not want to buy a green brand, because of their bad attitude towards green brands, there is a bad intention to buy a green brand. Second, they may not like the way green products advertise, namely in terms of format and content.

Effect of Green Brand on trust

The results showed that directly that the green brand has a positive and significant effect on trust. This shows that every increase in the green brand will also increase consumer confidence in the Tupperware product. This means that the better brand image of Tupperware increases consumer confidence in Tupperware products.

The mean value of the mean green brand of 2.91 respondents' answers indicates that respondents disagree that the Tupperware Brand is known for products that are environmentally friendly. Tupperware is well known among housewives as products that have good quality and are durable.

This research is in line with the research conducted by Dewi and Rastini (2016) where the results of the study show that green brands have a positive and significant effect on green trust in The Face Shop. Where the store, The Face Shop, sells all environmentally friendly products and the design of the shop is also designed to be minimal waste that can pollute the environment.

Effect of Green Product on Purchasing Decisions

The results showed that directly that green products have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This shows that every increase in green product will also increase consumer purchasing decisions to Tupperware products. Tupperware products with an environmentally friendly Tupperware concept make consumers decide to choose Tupperware products.

The average mean green product value of 2.99 respondents' answers indicates that respondents disagree, as well as purchasing decisions where the mean value is 2.95. This proves that the green product concept made by Tupperware has not made consumers decide to buy Tupperware. The low consumer decision to buy Tupperware products is evidenced from the respondent's answer to the statement that marketing done by Tupperware as an environmentally friendly product in accordance with the quality of its products is that most consumers answer less than 28 people and then disagree as many as 18 people.

The Tupperware Company confirms that Tupperware is a product that is environmentally friendly and does not endanger health which has been proven by meeting the USA FDA (Food and Drug Administration) standards as an environmentally friendly product because raw materials do not use toxic chemicals commonly used by other plastic manufacturers. And another advantage of Tupperware products lies in the lid where as a product that is safe for the environment and health of the lid is designed to keep stored food and beverages hygienic, not polluted so as to reduce the risk of stored food rot quickly. Keriteria delivered in accordance with the theory put forward by Remedios (2012) where innovations in the form of green products have advantages over other products. Green products are usually durable, non-toxic, and made from recyclable materials.

The results of this study are relevant to the research conducted by Lapian & Soegoto (2016); Syafrina (2016); Jaju

(2014); Maste (2015) and Pratama (2014) which show that green products have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Green products have a special characteristic as a product that prioritizes use not only thinking of mere needs, but also emphasizing the needs of the surrounding environment and health. Many similar products that are marketed do not apply environmentally friendly concepts, but are selling well in the market, this does not affect the marketing of environmentally friendly products, because environmentally friendly products generally market their products to market niches from the market of similar products.

Effect of Green Advertising on Purchasing Decisions

The results showed that directly that green products have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This shows that every increase in green product will also increase consumer purchasing decisions to Tupperware products. Tupperware products with an environmentally friendly Tupperware concept make consumers decide to choose Tupperware products.

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The results of this study indicate that green advertising has a positive and not significant effect on purchasing decisions. Where the green advertising carried by the company increases purchasing decisions. Green advertising is one of the factors that

influence consumers, meaning that green advertising owned by Tupperware is followed by purchasing decisions. Whereas for significant results, it means that the better the green advertising that consumers have, the better it will not change their purchasing decisions.

The results of respondents' answers to green advertising variables are known that the item statement about the influence of green advertising on the decision to buy Tupperware products is not as expected, with a frequency value (74) of respondents and an average (17.77). disagree with the statement, respondents did not care much about the advertisements displayed by Tupperware.

Based on the results of this study, it can be proven that the influence between green advertising variables on purchasing decisions has a positive and insignificant effect. This can be seen from the significance of 0.538 and the probability value of $0.592 > 0.05$, meaning that the hypothesis is rejected because green advertising has a positive and not significant effect on purchasing decisions. This means that the better marketing of green products made by green advertising does not affect the purchasing decisions of teachers at Beureunun Middle School.

This is also in accordance with research by Pawitaningtyas (2015) stating that green advertising does not affect consumers to make purchasing decisions directly, but green advertising can directly enhance brand image, the positive brand image will increase product purchasing decisions. And found the same thing with the conditions in the study at SMPN Beureunuen.

This is reinforced by the theory stated by Suhut (2002). Unlike prices, quality and other features the environmental impact of a product will not always be seen directly and may not directly affect the buyer. Thus, it is often abstract in nature and gives consumers the opportunity to act on environmental concerns.

Effect of Green Brand on Purchasing Decisions

The results showed that directly that green products have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This shows that every increase in green product will also increase consumer purchasing decisions to Tupperware products. Tupperware products with an environmentally friendly Tupperware concept make consumers decide to choose Tupperware products.

The average mean green product value of 2.99 respondents' answers indicates that respondents disagree, as well as purchasing decisions where the mean value is 2.95. This proves that the green product concept made by Tupperware has not made consumers decide to buy Tupperware. The low consumer decision to buy Tupperware products is evidenced from the respondent's answer to the statement that marketing done by Tupperware as an environmentally friendly product in accordance with the quality of its products is that most consumers answer less than 28 people and then disagree as many as 18 people.

Based on the research phenomenon, the green brand variable is a well-known brand with good quality. For example, Tupperware products are well-known brands of household appliances made of plastic, including storage containers, serving containers and some environmentally friendly kitchen utensils.

Green brands influence purchasing decisions. This is because consumers consider Tupperware an environmentally friendly product. Consumers who care about the environment realize that the Tupperware brand is in accordance with their needs and desires, so consumers decide to buy Tupperware products.

From the results of the respondents' answers for the green brand variable, it is known that the item statement about the influence of the green brand on the decision to purchase Tupperware products is as expected. This means that many teachers at SMPN Beureunuen agree with the

statement, with a frequency score (75) of respondents and an average (30.40). This means that products with the Tupperware brand are in line with the expectations of the teachers at SMPN Beureunuen.

Based on the results of this study, it can be proven that there is an influence between green brand variables on purchasing decisions. The first hypothesis which states that there is an influence between the green brand and the purchasing decision has been proven. This can be seen from the significance of 0.455 and the probability value of 0.650 <0.05. This means that green brands have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, thus the hypothesis is accepted.

This is also in accordance with Almaulidta's research (2015) with the title "The effect of green brand on purchasing decisions and satisfaction of Sony electronic products" and this study shows that there is a significant effect between the variable green brand (X) on the variable (Y1), namely purchasing decisions. And this was found the same thing as the conditions in the study at SMPN Beureunuen.

And this is reinforced by the theory stated by Praharjo (2013). Perception about the green brand is one of the strategies carried out by the company that the brand simply does not see aspects of profit but also looks at the environmental aspects. Environmental care ads that are properly communicated will make it easier for a green brand to be embedded in the minds of consumers. This will change consumer perceptions, so that it will influence purchasing decisions.

Effect of Trust in Purchasing Decisions

The results of the study indicate that trust has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. This means that the respondents' trust in Tupperware products owned by the average respondent is followed by the decision to purchase the product. Whereas for significant results, it means that the better the trust the respondents have, the better it will influence their purchasing

decisions. Trust has a positive effect because the statement on this variable leads to trust. To increase the confidence of respondents the company makes products in such a way according to the request of the respondent. So that respondents increasingly believed in Tupperware products and finally the respondents' decision to buy Tupperware products was higher.

From the results of the respondent's answers to the variable trust in the purchase decision, it is known that the statement item regarding the influence of trust in the decision to purchase Tupperware products is in accordance with what is expected. This means that many teachers at Beureunun Middle School agree with the statement with the frequency value (75) of the respondents. And the average (12,56). This means that the more respondents believe in Tupperware products, it greatly affects the purchasing decisions in the SMPN Beureunuen teacher environment.

Based on the results of this study it can be proven that there is an influence between the variables of trust in purchasing decisions. The first hypothesis which states that there is an influence of trust in purchasing decisions is proven. This can be seen from the results of significance of 6.047 and the significance value of the trust is $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the trust variable has a positive and significant effect on trust. Thus the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the more respondents believe in Tupperware products, the more respondents in making decisions to purchase Tupperware products.

The theory stated by Kotler and Keller (2012), trust is a cognitive component of the psychological factors. Trust relates to belief, that something is true or false on the basis of evidence, suggestion, authority, experience and intuition.

This is also in accordance with previous research, one of which was research by Anggraeni and Madiawati entitled "The influence of trust and quality of information on purchasing decisions online at the site www.traveloka.com". find

evidence that there is a positive and significant influence on trust in purchasing decisions. And this has the same conditions in research at SMPN Beureunuen.

Effect of Green Product on Purchasing Decisions Through Trust

The results of the study show that directly the green product influences the purchasing decision. while the indirect effect shows that the value of the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect. The value of total influence shows that with the role of trust can increase the influence of green product on purchasing decisions.

The green product concept Tupperware is believed by consumers to be environmentally friendly products. Consumers decide to buy Tupperware products because Tupperware products are believed to be quality products that are environmentally friendly and do not damage health like other types of plastic products.

This is appropriate as the theory stated by Anderson and Narus (1990) defines trust as follows: "Trust as a belief that another company will perform actions that will result in positive outcomes for firm while not taking actions that would result in negative outcomes " Based on the definition above trust is the belief of a company against other companies that other companies will provide a positive outcome.

This is also in accordance with previous research, one of which is related to the research of Darwin and Kunto, (2014) entitled "Analysis of the effect of service quality on customer loyalty with customer satisfaction and trust as an intervening variable in manulife Indonesia - Surabaya life insurance" And the results are the results of the study show there is a significant relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction, significant trust has an influence between customer loyalty and a significant influence between customer satisfaction and trust in customer loyalty.

Effect of Green Advertising on Purchasing Decisions Through Trust

The results showed that directly that green advertising had a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Whereas the indirect effect shows that the value of the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect. The value of indirect influence shows that with the role of trust can increase the influence of green advertising on purchasing decisions.

The contribution of green advertising through trust to determine purchasing decisions is directly proportional, meaning that every increase in the value of green advertising, consumer involvement will increase so that it indirectly affects the purchasing decision itself. There is a significant relationship but almost close to 0.05, this is because green advertising programs that have been run by Tupperware are less effective in creating consumer involvement. These programs do not provide information or messages about the green environment. This can be seen from the average answer to the questionnaire given to consumers who disagree about Tupperware which campaigns for environmental care, not yet characterized by environmental friendliness, both images and banners, and not yet able to load logos and certificates regarding environmental concerns.

The application of green advertising (X2) influences purchasing decisions (Y2) through trust (Y1). It can be seen that the contribution of green advertising through trust to determine purchasing decisions is inversely proportional, meaning that every increase in the green advertising value, consumer involvement will decrease so that it indirectly affects the purchasing decision itself. However, because the relationship between the three has a significance of approaching 0.05, this is because green advertising programs that have been run by Tupperware have not been effective in creating consumer involvement. Programs with environmentally friendly messages have not been maximally absorbed by consumers. This can be seen from the

average answer to the questionnaire given to consumers who disagree about Tupperware advertisements that campaign for environmental concerns, not yet characterized by environmental friendliness, both images and banners, and cannot yet contain logos and certificates regarding environmental concerns.

Effect of Green Brand on Purchasing Decisions Through Trust

The results of the study show that directly the green brand influences the purchasing decision. while the indirect effect shows that the value of the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect. The value of total influence shows that the role of trust can increase the indirect influence of green brands on purchasing decisions.

Trust is a will to depend on a product, service or on the basis of beliefs or expectations that result from credibility, good deeds and skills over performance (Chen, 2010). If consumer trust has grown towards a company, then the company has more value that will benefit the company. Therefore, purchasing decisions are influenced by consumers who have trusted the Tupperware brand that prioritizes a green brand. Schlosse (2016) argues that customer trust is a determinant of consumer purchase intentions, if buyers have experience of trust with the seller, they will have an increased purchase intention. Thus, trust becomes an intervening variable in purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The conclusions in this study are as follows:

1. Green products, green advertising and green brands partially have a positive and significant effect on consumer trust in Tupperware products at Beureunung Middle School
2. Green product, green brand and trust partially have a positive and significant effect on the decision to purchase

Tupperware products at Beureunun Middle School

3. Green advertising partially has a positive and insignificant effect on the decision to purchase Tupperware products at Beureunun Middle School
4. Green products, green advertising and green brands have a positive and significant effect on product purchase decisions through the trust of Tupperware at Beureunun Middle School

Recommendations

The suggestions presented in this study are as follows:

1. Tupperware raw materials consist of natural ingredients and do not contain hazardous chemicals, this makes Tupperware prone to eating mice and not all consumers know this. It is recommended that the company label the new product to be marketed about the weaknesses of this product, so that consumers do not feel disadvantaged. Because the product that has been bitten by a mouse cannot be exchanged.
2. Green advertising does not have a positive effect on purchasing decisions at Beureunun Middle School, it is hoped that the Tupperware Company should pay more attention to the content of the advertisements that will be delivered to consumers, considering that not all consumers are pro on green products.
3. The application of environmentally friendly product concepts to Tupperware is the right thing that companies do considering the target of Tupperware marketing is housewives in general. Making special eco-friendly logos on products should be done considering that eco-friendly product logos are only found on products that use box packaging only.
4. This study has a limited sample because it is only done in SMPN Beureunuen, it is hoped that further research will expand the research sample not only to

teachers in SMPN Beureunuen but expand to all teachers in Beureunuen.

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